

Synthesis of N-(2-Methyl-5, 7-Halo-4-Quinazolon-3-yl)-4-Aryl-1-Piperazinylacetamides as Anticonvulsants

S. S. TEWARI, M. I. HUSAIN* and G. C. SRIVASATVA

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow

Manuscript received 30 April 1979, revised 24 September 1979, accepted 9 January 1980

Twenty new N-(2-methyl-5, 7-halo-4-quinazolon-3-yl)-4-aryl-1-piperazinylacetamides were prepared by the condensation of an appropriate acetantranil with various 4-aryl-1-piperazinoacetic acid hydrazides. All of these compounds when screened for anticonvulsant activity against pentylenetetrazol-induced seizures in mice at a dose of 80 mg/kg were, however, found to be inactive.

LITERATURE survey has revealed that some derivatives of piperazine¹⁻⁵ and quinazolone⁶⁻⁸ have pronounced anticonvulsant properties. Piperazinoquinazolones⁹ have also been reported to possess anticonvulsant activity. In addition a few derivatives of acetamide such as 2,2-dialkylcyanoacetamides^{10,11} and in particular 2-ethyl-2-propyl cyanoacetamides have demonstrated significant anticonvulsant activity both against supra maximal electroshock and subcutaneous pentylenetetrazol induced seizures. In view of these observations, the authors have synthesized the title acetamides containing quinazolone and piperazine moieties, the presence of which was expected to enhance anticonvulsant properties. The scheme of their preparation is as follows: (X or X¹=H, Cl, Br or I and Y=*m*-CH₃; *p*-CH₃; *m*-Cl and *p*-Cl).

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

Acetantranils (IV): These were prepared by the condensation of an appropriate anthranilic acid^{12,13,14} with acetic anhydride according to a reported procedure¹⁵.

N-Aryl-piperazines (I): These were prepared by the method of Pollard *et al.*^{16,17}.

4-Aryl-1-piperazinoacetic acid ethylesters(II) and 4-Aryl-1-piperazinoacetic acid hydrazides(III) were prepared according to a known method¹⁸.

III, Y=3-Cl, m.p. 93-94° (60% yield), Found: N, 20.92%. C₁₂H₁₇N₄OCl, requires N, 21.30%.

III, Y=4-Cl, m. p. 110-112° (50% yield). Found: N, 20.78%. C₁₂H₁₇N₄OCl, requires N, 21.30%.

N-(2-Methyl-5, 7-halo-4-quinazolon-3-yl)-4-aryl-1-piperazinylacetamides (V):

A mixture of an appropriate acetantranil (.01M) and 4-aryl-1-piperazinoacetic acid hydrazide (.01M) was heated on a free flame for 15-20 mts. On cooling a jelly like mass separated out which was washed with petroleum ether (60-80°). The solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

The structures of the above compounds were supported by their IR spectra which showed bands at 3210-3150 cm⁻¹ (NH Str.), 1480-1445 cm⁻¹ (-CH₂-N<) and 1680 cm⁻¹ (C=O of sec. amide).

TABLE 1—N-(2-METHYL-5, 7-HALO 4-QUINAZOLON-3-YL)-4 ARYL-1-PIPFRAZINYLACETAMIDES* (V)

Sl. No.	X	X'	Y	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	N %	
						Found	Calcd.
1.	Br	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	190	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₅ O ₂ Br	14.51	14.89
2.	Br	Br	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	195-96	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₂ Br ₂	12.35	12.75
3.	I	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	108-10	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₅ O ₂ I	13.10	13.53
4.	Br	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	63-65	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂ ClBr	13.86	14.27
5.	Br	Br	<i>p</i> -Cl	218	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₅ O ₂ ClBr ₂	11.81	12.29
6.	I	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	132-34	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂ ClI	13.32	13.02
7.	Br	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	148	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₅ O ₂ Br	15.26	14.89
8.	Br	Br	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	112-13	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₂ Br ₂	12.30	12.75
9.	I	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	139-40	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₅ O ₂ I	13.27	13.53
10.	Br	H	<i>m</i> -Cl	70	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂ ClBr	13.75	14.27
11.	Br	Br	<i>m</i> -Cl	119-20	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₅ O ₂ ClBr ₂	11.85	12.29
12.	Cl	H	<i>m</i> -Cl	150	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂ Cl ₂	15.37	15.69
13.	I	H	<i>m</i> -Cl	148-49	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂ ClI	13.43	13.02
14.	Cl	Cl	<i>m</i> -Cl	130-32	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₅ O ₂ Cl ₃	14.25	14.56
15.	Cl	Cl	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	200	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₂ Cl ₂	14.89	15.21
16.	Cl	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	174	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₅ O ₂ Cl	16.17	16.45
17.	Cl	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	150-51	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂ Cl ₂	15.56	15.69
18.	Cl	Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	255	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₅ O ₂ Cl ₃	14.13	14.56
19.	Cl	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	155	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₅ O ₂ Cl	16.13	16.45
20.	Cl	Cl	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	125	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₂ Cl ₂	14.83	15.21

*Yields ranged from 50 to 60%.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to Dr. R.C. Simal of C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for anticonvulsant screening of the compounds and to Dr. Kirpa Shankar of K.G.M.C., Lucknow, for helpful discussions. Thanks are also due to Dr. S. P. Tewarson, Principal, Lucknow Christian College, for granting academic leave and the U.G.C. for providing teacher fellowship to one of us (G.C.S.).

References

1. B. LUEKA-SABSTEL and A. ZEI, *Diss. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1971, 23, 135.
2. V. K. AGARWAL, K. C. SAH, S. NAGAR and S. S. PARMAR, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1970, 312, 964.
3. A. K. CHATURVEDI and S. S. PARMAR, *Curr. Sci.*, 1972, 41, 253.
4. Lakeside Laboratories Inc., *Brit.*, 1963, 936, 764, *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, 61, 8322f.
5. *Belg. Pat.*, 1963, 623, 058.
6. M. L. GUJRAL, P. N. SAXENA and R. P. KOHLI, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1957, 45, 207.
7. C. BIANCHI and A. DAVID, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1960, 12, 501.
8. A. K. CHATURVEDI and S. S. PARMAR, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1972, 34, 72.
9. SURENDRA S. PARMAR, A. K. CHATURVEDI, A. CHAUDHARY and STANLEY J. BRUMLEV, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1974, 63, 357.
10. HERBERT F. SCHWARTZ II, LEE F. WORRELL and JAMES N. DELGADO, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1967, 56, 80.
11. HERBERT F. SCHWARTZ II, ROBERT G. BROWN, EUGENE ISAACSON and JAMES N. DELGADO, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1968, 57, 1530.
12. MARGARAT M. ENDICOTT, BETTY W. ALDEN and MARY L. SHERRILL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1303.
13. ALVIN S. WHEELER and W. M. OATES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 32, 770.
14. CARL J. KLEMME and JAMES H. HUNTER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, 5, 230.
15. SURENDRA S. PARMAR and R. C. ARORA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1967, 10, 1182.
16. C. B. POLLARD and M. S. AGRUSS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 2199.
17. C. B. POLLARD and THOMAS H. WICKER JR., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 1853.
18. A. K. SENGUPTA, K. C. AGARWAL and M. MUSHTAQ, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 961.